

THE CRUCIAL ROLE OF UZBEK LANGUAGE IN MASTERING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Abstract. *This article highlights the vital role of one's native language, in our case, Uzbek language, in successfully learning a foreign language. It argues that understanding the grammatical structures and vocabulary of Uzbek language can significantly help learners overcome the challenges of acquiring new languages. The article emphasizes the importance of leveraging the strengths of one's native language to facilitate the acquisition of new linguistic skills.*

Keywords: *foreign language, language learning, Uzbek language, knowledge, teaching.*

Today, our nation is actively implementing measures aimed at enhancing the education and development of our youth, the future leaders of our country. The focus is on nurturing their scientific potential and preparing them for a rapidly changing world.

To ensure our youth are not left behind, and to facilitate the seamless integration of global best practices, there is a strong emphasis on promoting foreign language learning. This initiative aims to bridge cultural divides and encourage the exchange of knowledge and experiences across borders.

The implementation of innovative foreign language teaching methods is a key aspect of this initiative. By equipping our youth with proficiency in foreign languages, we empower them to engage with the world and contribute to its advancement.

Learning a foreign language inevitably presents its own unique challenges. The root of these challenges often lies in factors we overlook or take for granted. One such factor is the significant impact our native language has on our ability to learn a foreign language.

As Uzbek scholar N. Rajabov aptly states, "One of the most crucial aspects of foreign language learning is the theoretical comparative study of the native language with the target language". The knowledge and insights gained from this comparative analysis significantly enhance the practical application of the language.

The global prominence of English language continues to grow, opening doors to vast opportunities for those who master it. In Uzbekistan, English is gaining significant popularity among young people, with the demand for English language learning steadily increasing.

However, due to the lack of a close linguistic relationship between Uzbek and English, the phenomenon of allomorphy (differences in phonetic realizations of the same morpheme) is particularly noticeable, especially in phonetics. Uzbek speakers encounter a number of linguistic hurdles as they familiarize themselves with English phonetics.

While English grammar (syntax and morphology) is often considered easier to learn compared to other foreign languages like German, Russian, French, or Chinese, its phonetics and pronunciation rules can be quite challenging. As English linguist Julian Northbrook aptly notes, "Learning English is much easier if your native language has a similar number of sounds as English".

In essence, a thorough understanding of the similarities and differences between Uzbek and English, particularly in phonetics, can significantly enhance the learning process and overcome the inherent challenges.

Let's consider the German phrase "Wer will, der kann", which is translated literally as "Who wants, that can". However, we can translate it more effectively and vividly into Uzbek as "Qimirlagan qir oshar" (meaning "Whoever is willing, can achieve anything"). This translation captures the essence of the phrase more powerfully, using the richness of Uzbek language.

Similarly, the phrase "Daheim ist es am besten" is translated literally as "At home, it is the best". But, by rendering it as "O'z uying, o'lan to'shaging" (meaning "Your own home, your own bed"), we create a more nuanced and evocative translation. Such examples abound in foreign language learning.

Educators recognize that students who have a deep understanding of their native language find it easier to learn additional languages. These learners naturally compare languages, facilitating language integration. In academia, the "comparative" approach to learning is widely recognized as a valuable method.

Just as we strategize before embarking on any long-term endeavor, achieving success in mastering a foreign language requires a strong foundation—a solid understanding of our native language. Koichiro Matsuura, the former Director-General of UNESCO, aptly captured the essence of this connection in his 2003 speech on International Mother Language Day: "Why is there such emphasis on the mother tongue? It is because languages are the unique expression of the full range of human creativity. As a tool for communication, understanding, and thought, language shapes how we see the world. It doesn't matter if a person also knows other languages". A deep appreciation for one's native language lays a solid foundation for acquiring other languages quickly, easily, and effectively

Consider, for example, simultaneous translation. This is the most challenging form of translation, requiring the interpreter to translate a speaker's words almost simultaneously, without any time for preparation. The interpreter must listen, understand, translate, and speak all at once. This intricate process requires a simultaneous translator to perform multiple operations simultaneously.

The connection between language and culture is profound, making our native language a powerful tool in our journey to master new languages.

While learning a foreign language can seem like stepping into an entirely new world, your native language, Uzbek, plays a crucial role in your success. Here's why:

1. Building a Strong Linguistic Foundation:

- **Understanding Grammar:** Uzbek's grammatical structure, although unique, shares similarities with other languages, particularly Turkic languages. This understanding can help you grasp core grammar concepts in other languages more easily.

- **Vocabulary Development:** Many Uzbek words have cognates (words with similar origins) in other languages, especially those with Indo-European roots. Recognizing these similarities can accelerate your vocabulary expansion in foreign languages.

2. Enhancing Cognitive Skills:

- **Analytical Thinking:** Learning Uzbek, with its rich grammar and complex sentence structures, strengthens your analytical thinking skills. This ability to dissect and analyze language is essential for understanding and mastering any new language.

• **Memory and Learning:** The process of learning Uzbek, with its diverse vocabulary and phonetic system, enhances your memory and learning capacity. These skills translate directly to learning new languages, enabling you to acquire and retain information more effectively.

3. Cultural Awareness:

• **Bridging Cultures:** Understanding Uzbek culture and its linguistic nuances provides a valuable perspective on the cultural context of other languages. This cultural awareness facilitates deeper comprehension and fosters a richer learning experience.

4. Boosting Confidence:

• **Transferable Skills:** The skills you develop while learning Uzbek, such as listening, speaking, reading, and writing, are transferable to any foreign language you choose to learn. This confidence in your abilities will motivate you and enhance your overall learning experience.

In essence, your mastery of Uzbek provides a valuable foundation for learning foreign languages. It equips you with the cognitive skills, cultural awareness, and linguistic understanding necessary to navigate the journey of language acquisition successfully.

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